

**Synthesis and Characterisation of some
Bivalent Metal Ion Complexes of Thiocyanate
or Iodide and Thiocarbohydrazide**

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It is evident from literature that no attempt have been made to synthesise above-mentioned bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Cd metal thiocyanate or iodide complexes with thiocarbohydrazide as stabilising ligand and the present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of such complexes.

Experimental

Reactions of thiocyanate or iodide and thiocarbohydrazide (Htcz) with the above-mentioned bivalent metal ions were conducted in different molar ratios. The solid products obtained were separated, washed and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal acetates and other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were dried by usual procedures and distilled. Htcz¹ was prepared by reacting hydrazine hydrate with CS₂ (m.p. 174°).

Preparation of complexes: Mixed ligand complexes were prepared by mixing an aqueous solution of metal acetate (50 ml, 0.005 mol) with an aqueous solution (50 ml) of potassium thiocyanate or potassium iodide (0.005 mol/0.01 mol). To it, aqueous solution (50 ml) of thiocarbohydrazide (0.005 mol) was added slowly with constant stirring. In case of copper, the complexes were precipitated immediately after mixing the reactants. However, in case of cobalt, nickel, zinc and cadmium complexes, the solution was neutralised by adding a very dilute solution of ammonium hydroxide. As soon as mixture attained neutral point, addition of ammonium hydroxide solution (1–2 drops) separated the complex. The products were filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal contents of the complexes were determined using standard methods².

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra at I.I.T., Madras. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature (25 ± 2°) using a vibrating sample magnetometer at USIC, University of Roorkee and the corrections were made³. The thermal studies were carried out at Panjab University, Chandigarh. The specimens were heated at the rate of 10° min⁻¹ and heated alumina was used as standard.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicate the general formula of the complexes as MX₂(Htcz).H₂O, MX(tcza) and M₂X₂(tcza)₂, where M = bivalent metal ion, X = thiocyanate or iodide. The complexes were found to be insoluble in most of the common organic solvents, did not melt even up to 250° (except zinc complex) and non-hygroscopic.

The ir bands of free ligand Htcz, were obtained at 3 280s and 3 200–3 100br (NH), 1 640, 1 625 (δNH₂), 925 (C=S + δ CNN + νCN) and 745 cm⁻¹ (C=S). In the metal complexes lowering of ν_{NH} (3 240–3 210) and δ_{NH₂} (1 600–1 585 cm⁻¹) bands is due to M–N bonding. It is further confirmed from far-infrared spectra of the complexes in which a band is observed at 520–480 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 4). The band at 745 cm⁻¹ in Htcz shifted to lower side (720–710 cm⁻¹) in the complexes indicating the M–S bond formation. The coordination of nitrogen bonded thiocyanate group to metal has been confirmed by ν_{C–N} and ν_{C–S} modes of vibration at 2 080–2 040 and 840–780 cm⁻¹ respectively, in case of the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. Support for bridging thiocyanate groups M–SCN–M comes from presence of bands at 2 080 (C–N) and 780–720 cm⁻¹ (C–S). Thus, the results indicate tenden-

tate nature of Htcz and bonding in M(II)–SCN–Htcz complex takes place through nitrogen and sulphur atoms. In M(II)–I–Htcz complexes, the bonds due to ν_{N–H} and ν_{C–S} mode of vibrations are also observed in the above regions. Thus, bonding in the iodide complexes also takes place through nitrogen and sulphur atoms. The presence of water molecule within the coordination sphere is supported by the appearance of bands at 3 600–3 500 (OH), 1 670–1 650 (HOH deformation) and 950–900 cm⁻¹ (H₂O rocking) in the spectra of the complexes.

The electronic spectrum of Co(SCN)₂(Htcz).H₂O complex showed two absorption bands around 9 200 and 19 500 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to excited states terms ⁴T_{2g}(ν₁) and ⁴T_{1g}(P)(ν₃) respectively arising from ⁴T_{1g}(F) ground state term. The effective magnetic moment value of 5.01 B.M. coupled with electronic spectrum confirm the octahedral geometry^{3,6}. Nickel(II) formed Ni₂(SCN)₂(tcza)₂.2H₂O and Ni₂I₂(tcza)₂.2H₂O complexes. Ni₂(SCN)₂(tcza)₂.2H₂O gave three main absorption bands at 8 800, 15 700 and 24 100 cm⁻¹ and may be assigned to excited states ³T_{2g}(ν₁), ³T_{1g}(ν₂) and ³T_{1g}(P)(ν₃) respectively arising from ³A_{2g}(F) ground state term. A band at 11 900 cm⁻¹ may be due to spin-forbidden transition ³A_{2g} → ¹E_g. The magnetic moment values of 2.92 and 2.80 B.M. coupled with electronic spectra of the nickel complexes indicated octahedral geometry⁶. Copper(II) formed Cu(SCN)(tcza) and CuI(tcza) complexes. The absorption band obtained at 21 900 and 20 650 cm⁻¹ respectively, were characteristic of square-planar geometry⁶. Another band around 27 000 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to charge transfer band⁷. The effective magnetic moment values of 1.95 and 1.83 B.M. were in agreement with the required range (1.70–2.20 B.M.) for d⁹ system. Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes are diamagnetic as expected for d¹⁰ configuration.

Thermal analyses of the complexes were carried out up to 1000°. Ni₂(SCN)₂(tcza)₂.2H₂O loses both the water molecules at 90° with a mass loss of 8.26% (theoretical 7.23%). In the second step, removal of Htcz is indicated at 350° with a mass loss of 50.4% (theoretical 45.4%). The evolution of SO₂ could be identified with an endothermic peak on DTA curve at 680° with a mass of 58.7% (theoretical 58.0%). In the final step, the total mass loss is 74.4% (theoretical 77.7%) with an endothermic peak at 880°, indicating the formation of NiO. The thermal degradation of Zn₂I₂(tcza)₂.2H₂O follows in the same pattern.

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